

Governing AI Surveillance through Legal and Social Knowledge: An Islamic and Anthropological Framework

Abdullah Omran

Abdullah Omran is a PhD candidate in Middle Eastern Languages and Cultures at Indiana University Bloomington. He is a digital ethnographer whose work explores the intersection between technological advancement and Islamic legal studies.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) now plays a central role in military and security systems across the Arab world. Governments use AI for predictive surveillance, signal analysis (such as Egypt's use of facial recognition systems at public gatherings and the UAE's deployment of predictive policing algorithms in urban centers), automated screening, and counterterrorism intelligence, often through security agencies rather than civilian institutions (Sakr & Hakme 2025). Studies of AI militarization also show how states integrate these tools into surveillance and weapon systems that have certainly reshaped domestic control and regional power relations (Sarkin & Sotoudehfar 2024).

When automated systems decide who gets monitored, detained, or targeted, they do not always do so accurately. They raise the practical question about whether probabilistic suspicion can ever justify state coercion. This question shapes whether AI-driven security systems distinguish between a poet and a plotter, a dissenter and a militant, or a private grievance and a public threat. Islamic legal tradition offers a structured response to precisely these questions. It provides categorical distinctions that map different forms of polit-

ical expression and wrongdoing to different thresholds of permissible state intrusion. In Islamic law, not all political acts are treated the same. A person offering sincere advice to a ruler is not placed in the same category as someone inciting rebellion; each is judged differently, with different rights and limits on what the state can do. That means the state must ask what kind of act it is, who is doing it, and whether it crosses a moral or legal line. Privacy, according to Islamic law, is a binding limit on what the state may know (Almutairi 2020; Al-Shamari 2024; Hayat 2007). And it provides a legal taxonomy that tells us who is entitled to what kind of privacy protection. The challenge is how to encode these limits into the machines themselves. This piece argues that anthropology functions as a method for making uncertainty visible within the system and for ensuring that contested meaning slows down decision-making rather than speeding it up. Put differently, ethnographic specificity offers discernible, though not always clear cut, identificatory markers of social groups and, more importantly, of their practices. As such, it lends legal categories in intra Muslim conflict the legibility necessary for AI assisted surveillance systems to

distinguish behavior in ways consistent with appropriate actionable intelligence.

One might reasonably ask why authoritarian and security-oriented states would accept privacy and cultural-differentiation constraints on AI-driven surveillance and targeting. The answer is not that such states suddenly value privacy, but that AI changes how security decisions are made and where responsibility sits. Once states rely on AI systems that sort people, speech, or locations into risk categories before human review, errors and intrusions are no longer isolated incidents. Rather, they become routine system outputs. Research on AI assisted targeting shows that these systems tend to narrow judgment, encourage reliance on automated recommendations, and blur accountability. This creates real risks of escalation, legal exposure, and loss of control for security agencies themselves (Dorsey 2026; Blanchard and Bruun 2025). In addition, contextual and cultural constraints, such as linguistic nuance, religious context, and local political discourse, can improve performance.

Work on Arabic Natural Language Processing (NLP) shows that systems trained on simplified threat categories regularly misread dialectal, indirect, or context-dependent political speech, leading to false positives that expand surveillance beyond actionable risk (Haj Ahmed et al. 2024; Charfi et al. 2024). When AI outputs feed directly into security workflows, these errors are costly. Treating interpretation as part of classification, rather than noise, reduces this problem.

The stakes become clear when AI systems collapse legally distinct categories into a single risk continuum. Contemporary targeting and surveillance models treat activists, civilians, and militants as variations on the same

probabilistic object, assigning scores that justify intervention without requiring categorical legal proof (Gordon et al. 2023; McKendrick 2019). In Egypt, counterterrorism surveillance applies the same profiling logic to peaceful political activity as it does to militant networks (Human Rights Watch 2024). In Palestine, Israeli AI systems, such as Lavender and Gospel, generate large suspect lists through pattern analysis, merging civilians and combatants under conditions of limited human review (Amnesty International 2022). These cases illustrate a structural failure of AI mediated governance in the sense that decision systems act on calculated risk rather than a legally meaningful distinction.

While privacy concerns about AI surveillance arise across national contexts, Islamic jurisprudence offers a particularly structured framework for addressing them, but it places a greater burden on the state to avoid arbitrary automated suspicion detection. Islamic jurisprudence distinguishes three legal categories relevant to internal security. *Bughāt* are principled dissenters who oppose the state on the basis of plausible legal interpretation (*ta'wīl*). Their private deliberations and political organizing are protected, and surveillance is prohibited absent active hostilities. *Muhāribūn* are agents of indiscriminate harm who destabilize public order. Islamic law permits limited intervention against them but requires visible wrongdoing rather than probabilistic inference. *Mujrimūn* are ordinary offenders whose wrongdoing is personal. They enjoy the strongest privacy protections, as private vice and association do not justify intrusion (Al-Dawoody 2011).

Read as a governance framework, these categories specify how privacy should structure the design and use of AI surveillance. In the case of *bughāt*, design treats privacy as a

hard limit: political dissent grounded in *ta'wīl* does not justify invasive data collection, and AI systems' access should be restricted to publicly available information unless conduct clearly shifts into open hostilities. For *muhāribūn*, governance allows narrower intrusions but only after wrongdoing becomes visible and public. Predictive assessments, which estimate future risk from statistical patterns rather than proven wrongdoing, may inform attention but cannot serve as the legal basis for breaching privacy or escalating intervention. For *mujrimūn*, AI profiling is prohibited without concrete evidence of an offense. The difficulty is that AI systems do not recognize these legal thresholds on their own. They classify speech, relationships, and behavior as features rather than as legally situated acts.

The mismatch between legal categories and machine classification motivates a focus on anthropology, which examines how contextual interpretation can help enforce privacy boundaries within AI-based governance. In this framework, anthropological insight contributes to AI governance by shaping how systems are trained to interpret meaning under contextual uncertainty, instead of by expanding the scope of data they ingest. Rather than using personal data, this approach relies on short, anonymous examples of common speech, like sermons or protest chants. These examples help AI understand language and context without monitoring real people. Prior work on aligning AI training to cultural values shows that scenario-based materials are especially effective in post-training (AlKhamissi et al. 2025). They guide how systems reason about language without entangling interpretation with personal traces or real-world monitoring.

Within this framework, annotating the output data is limited to recording multiple plausible interpretations for the said scenarios rather than producing a single resolved label. The disagreement, rooted in the availability of multiple interpretations, is often constitutive of meaning rather than a sign of error, particularly in political, religious, or culturally embedded speech (Geertz 1973). Technical work on disagreement-aware learning supports this view by showing that models trained on unaggregated or plural annotations are better able to recognize boundary cases and uncertainty, rather than clustering contested meanings into confident predictions (Rodríguez Barroso et al. 2024).

Operationally, this means that ambiguity causes the system to pause or defer action rather than escalate automatically. The governance effect comes from how the system is trained to behave. Using de identified scenarios and retaining interpretive disagreement teaches the system to reason about context without following individuals and to acknowledge uncertainty rather than hide it. Privacy is enforced through these design choices, which shape how meaning is interpreted and how action is limited, rather than through later restrictions on data use.♦

References

- Al Dawoody, Ahmed. 2011. *The Islamic Law of War: Justifications and Regulations*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- AlKhamissi, Mai, Yunze Xiao, Badr AlKhamissi, and Mona Diab. 2025. "Hire Your Anthropologist! Rethinking Culture Benchmarks Through an Anthropological Lens." *arXiv* preprint, arXiv:2510.05931.

- Almutairi, S. E. 2020. "The Shari'a Approach to Contemporary Problems of Mass Surveillance." *Muslim World Journal of Human Rights* 17 (1): 1–24. <https://www.degruyterbrill.com/document/doi/10.1515/mwjhr-2020-0007/html>.
- Al Shamari, K. S. 2024. "Exclusion of Evidence and Its Impact on Criminal Justice: A Comparative Study." *Arab Law Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15730255-bja10143>.
- Amnesty International. 2022. *Automated Apartheid: How Facial Recognition Fragments, Segregates and Controls Palestinians in the Occupied Territories*. London: Amnesty International.
- Ashraf, Y., Y. Wang, B. Gu, P. Nakov, and T. Baldwin. 2024. "Arabic Dataset for LLM Safe-guard Evaluation." *arXiv* preprint. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2410.17040>.
- Blanchard, Alexander, and Laura Bruun. 2025. *Autonomous Weapon Systems and AI Enabled Decision Support Systems in Military Targeting: A Comparison and Recommended Policy Responses*. Stockholm: Stockholm International Peace Research Institute. <https://doi.org/10.55163/YQBY3151>
- Charfi, Anis, Mabrouka Besghaier, Raghda Akasheh, Andria Atalla, and Wajdi Zaghouani. 2024. "Hate Speech Detection with ADHAR: A Multi Dialectal Hate Speech Corpus in Arabic." *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2024.1391472>.
- Dorsey, Jessica. 2026. "The Erosion of Human(e) Judgement in Targeting? Quantification Logics, AI Enabled Decision Support Systems and Proportionality Assessments in International Humanitarian Law." *International Review of the Red Cross*, FirstView: 1–31. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1816383125100969>.
- Geertz, Clifford. 1973. *The Interpretation of Cultures: Selected Essays*. New York: Basic Books.
- Gordon, Neve, Nicola Perugini, and Yotam Feldman. 2023. "Humanitarian Violence and the Rise of Algorithmic Targeting." *Journal of Genocide Research* 25 (4): 1–19.
- Haj Ahmed, Ahmed, Rui Jie Yew, Xerxes Minocher, and Suresh Venkatasubramanian. 2024. "Navigating Dialectal Bias and Ethical Complexities in Levantine Arabic Hate Speech Detection." *arXiv* preprint, arXiv:2412.10991.
- Hayat, M. A. 2007. "Privacy and Islam: From the Qur'an to Data Protection in Pakistan." *Information & Communications Technology Law* 16 (2): 137–148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13600830701532043>.
- Human Rights Watch. 2024. *'Security Forces and the Algorithm': Digital Surveillance and Political Repression in Egypt*. New York: Human Rights Watch.
- McKendrick, David. 2019. *Risk, Probability, and Security Decision Making*. London: Routledge.

Rodríguez Barroso, Nuria, Eugenio Martínez Cámara, Jose Camacho Collados, M. Victoria Luzón, and Francisco Herrera. 2024. “Federated Learning for Exploiting Annotators’ Disagreements in Natural Language Processing.” *Transactions of the Association for Computational Linguistics* 12: 630–648. https://doi.org/10.1162/tacl_a_00664.

Sakr, G. E., and O. Hakme. 2025. “The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Military and Security in the MENA.” In *AI in the Middle East for Growth and Business*, 363–383. Cham: Springer.

Sarkin, Jeremy Julian, and Saba Sotoudehfar. 2024. “Artificial Intelligence and Arms Races in the Middle East: The Evolution of Technology and Its Implications for Regional and International Security.” *Defence and Security Analysis* 40 (1): 97–119. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14751798.2024.2302699>.